

Crop Demand and Price Forecasting with AI Farmer Assistant

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Abstract

This research addresses a major issue in Sri Lanka's agricultural planning, which is reactive rather than proactive, short-term focused crop overproduction or underproduction, and price crashes. These mismatched factors cause financial losses for farmers, crop surplus, price fluctuations, unnecessary food imports, postharvest wastages, and a negative impact on farmers, consumers, and the government. This study was done to develop a proactive, data-driven solution to address this issue and help prevent surplus production and price crashes. The study presents a design of an AI-powered software system that predicts upcoming monthly crop production and consumption in cooperation with a farmer registration system for each crop to maintain crop production and prevent excess or dearth, which leads to market instability. The system also suggests alternative crops if a particular crop exceeds its margin of production based on farmers' areas, weather, and crop cycles in that area. Additionally, this offers a marketplace for farmers to buy tools, equipment, seeds, and crops. Technological approach makes advanced machine learning models to implement, such as Random Forest, Decision Trees, and K-Nearest Neighbors, with the implementation of a chatbot assistant and Internet of Things (IoT) for real-time validation. This solution uses both mobile and web technologies that support cross platforms to deliver an easy-to-use approach for farmers. This research discovers that the integration of machine learning and AI chatbots can effectively help farmers to reduce crop surplus and price crashes. This proactive system suggests strategic planting guidance, reduces financial risks, and real-time market demand analysis. This system enhances Sri Lanka's agricultural efficiency and sustainability with promising results.

Keywords: *Crop Prediction, Price Forecasting, Surplus Prevention, Machine Learning, Agricultural Chatbot.*